

ISSN- 0301-1216

Indian J. Prev. Soc. Med. Vol. 56, No.3, 2025

Medication Adherence and its associated risk factors among Type II Diabetes Mellitus patients in Urban Prayagraj

Shushil Kumar Mishra¹, Khurshid Parveen², Anubha Srivastava³, Gyan Prakash⁴, Richa Singh⁵

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The World Health Organization has identified diabetes Mellitus (DM) as an important non-communicable disease that demands immediate global attention. In patients with DM musculoskeletal and vascular complication negatively affects the quality of life (QoL). In India, medication adherence among Type 2 DM patients is a significant concern, with various factors influencing adherence levels. To prevent the development of fatal complications associated with DM, glycaemic control is required. To achieve that goal, it is necessary to encourage patients to adhere to therapeutic regimens, change their life style, and follow the recommendations of their clinicians. **Objectives:** To measure medication adherence, to determine the various risk factors affecting medication adherence, to find out the association of health-related quality of life (HRQOL) with medication adherence among patients having Type 2 DM aged 18 years or above, residing in urban Prayagraj. **Study Design:** Cross sectional descriptive study. **Methods:** The study is conducted on primary data collected through pretested structured schedule method. Adherence to diabetic medications was assessed by an eight-item content validated questionnaire developed based on previous literature (modified Morisky scale). Quality of life was assessed using WHOQOL-BREF questionnaire and it is categorized in quartiles. **Results:** The majority of participants were in aged above 50 years, accounting for 41.59%. The highest proportion had no formal education 31.03%. Among the 107 participants with high medication adherence, 9.38% reported low, 30.25% reported medium and 67.53% reported high quality of life. **Conclusion:** Only 35% participants had high medical adherence and other were in low medical adherence. About two-fifth participants were in second quartile of quality of life score and very few 10% participants were in fourth quartile of quality of life score.

Key words: Adherence, Morisky scale, WHOQOL-BREF scale, Diabetes mellitus, Quality of life, Knowledge.

Author(s) Details:

1. JR-3, Department of Community Medicine, Motilal Nehru Medical College, Prayagraj.
Email: devajaiganpati@gmail.com;
2. Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Motilal Nehru Medical College, Prayagraj,
Email: drkpraveen@gmail.com; 831874173.
3. Professor & Head, Department of Community Medicine, Moti Lal Nehru Medical College, Prayagraj,
Mob. 9453029922.
4. Professor, Department of Pathology, Principal, M.L.N. Medical College, Prayagraj, U.P.
Email: ggyanji@yahoo.com ; Mob. 8707654761.
5. Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, MLN Medical College Prayagraj;
Email : conscious.richa@gmail.com; Mob. 9140600490.

Corresponding Address: Shushil Kumar Mishra, MD Student, Department of Community Medicine, Motilal Nehru Medical College, Prayagraj- 211002.

Citation: Mishra SK, Parveen K, Hassan MA, Misra V, Prakash G, Srivastava A, Singh R. Medication Adherence and its associated risk factors among Type II Diabetes Mellitus patients in Urban Prayagraj Indian J Prev Soc Med. 2025; 56 (3): 405-413. DOI [https:// doi.org/](https://doi.org/)

Sequence of Article: | Submission: 18.06.2025 | Accepted: 20.07.2025 | Published: 30.09.2025

Prior Publication: Nil; **Source of Funding:** Nil; **Conflicts of Interest:** None, **Article # 805/1182**

Introduction

Diabetes is a chronic disease that occurs either when the pancreas does not produce enough insulin or when the body cannot effectively use the insulin it produces. Insulin is a hormone that regulates blood glucose. Hyperglycaemia, is a common effect of uncontrolled diabetes and over time leads to serious damage to many of the body's systems, especially the nerves and blood vessels.¹

The prevalence of DM is increasing rapidly; type 2 DM frequency in particular is rising in parallel with the epidemic of obesity. In the United States, DM prevalence was at greater than 8% of the population, increasing with age. A significant portion of persons with DM are undiagnosed. DM is attended by serious morbidity and significant mortality; it is the fifth leading cause of death worldwide.²

Type 2 DM is one of the fastest growing health challenges of the 21st century and International Diabetes Federation estimates that about 463 million adults are living with diabetes worldwide.³

India stands second in the world after China in terms of prevalence of DM with 77 million living with DM in 2019, which is expected to rise to 101 million by 2030. In 2017, globally deaths due to diabetes was estimated to be 4 million. Adequate managements of hyperglycaemia in DM is important to prevent or delay complications and improve quality of life.⁴

Diabetes facts and figures show the growing global burden for individuals, families, and countries. The latest IDF Diabetes Atlas (2025) reports that 11.1% – or 1 in 9 – of the adult population (20-79 years) is living with diabetes, with over 4 in 10 unaware that they have the condition.

By 2050, IDF projections show that 1 in 8 adults, approximately 853 million, will be living with diabetes, an increase of 46%. Over 90% of people with diabetes have Type 2 diabetes, which is driven by socio-economic, demographic, environmental, and genetic factors. The key contributors to the rise in Type 2 diabetes include: (a) Urbanization, (b) An ageing population (c) Decreasing levels of physical activity (d) Increasing overweight and obesity prevalence

The World Health Organization has identified DM as an important non-communicable disease that demands immediate global attention. In patients with DM musculoskeletal and vascular complications negatively affects the QoL. To prevent the development of fatal complications associated with DM, glycaemic control is required. To achieve that goal, it is necessary to encourage patients to adhere to therapeutic regimens, change their life style, and follow the recommendations of their clinicians. Research involving outpatients reported that more than 50% do not adhere to the correct medicine administration and dosage.⁵

Adherence is defined as “the extent to which a person’s behaviour, taking medication, following a prescribed diet, and/or executing lifestyle changes corresponds with agreed recommendations from the health care provider”. A number of reviews found that the average adherence rates among patients with chronic diseases are only 50% in developed countries, and this is expected to be lower in developing countries because of the limited health resources and accessibility to health care.⁶

Aim: The aim of the study is to assess the level of medication adherence among study subjects.

Objectives:

1. To measure medication adherence among patients having Type 2 DM in the study subjects.
2. To determine the various risk factors affecting adherence to medication in the study subjects.
3. To find out the association of HRQOL with adherence to medication in the study subjects.

Material and Methods

Study Setting: The study is carried out among adults 18 years and above residing in the urban area of Prayagraj District, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Study Design: Cross sectional descriptive study

Study Population: All the known Type 2DM cases aged 18 years or above residing in urban Prayagraj.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Any known T2DM case, aged 18 years and above of both genders.
2. On treatment for at least 6 months.
3. Those who had given consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patient from outside of the district or from the rural area of Prayagraj.
2. Seriously ill, speech problem, psychiatric disorder etc.

Study Duration: The research study work was conducted from June 2023 to May, 2024.

Sample size: Kavitha et al (2017)⁷, discussed about the adherence among Type 2 DM patients. They obtained 28% poor adherence level along with 30% overall adherence. Here we estimated the sample size by using poor adherence level (28%) for Type2DM patient for our study at 5% of Type-1 error along with 20% relative error. The estimated size is 247 and assuming 18% non-respondent rate the final sample size for this study is 301.22 but findings are presented on 303 study subjects.

Sample selection: Case selection and recruitment were initiated after obtaining approval from the institutional ethics committee. A list of individuals with T2DM (on at least 6 month of treatment) was retrieved from the diabetic clinic of the government tertiary care institution in the district. All those from other districts and the ones residing in rural areas were excluded. From the rest of the patients remaining in the list, 303 patients were selected randomly through computer generated random number.

Data collection: They were contacted via telephone or in person to make sure they were willing to participate in the study and then they were visited and data was obtained by personal interview. Written informed consent was obtained from all study participants prior to the interview. The research tools included predesigned structured schedule with details of socioeconomic variables, laboratory investigations, and medications. Adherence to diabetic medications was assessed by an eight-item content validated questionnaire developed based on previous literature (modified Morisky scale). Fasting blood sugar value (FBS) taken within the past 6 months and rough estimate of self-reported monthly expenditure for treating T2DM were also collected. Respondents who were non-adherent to diabetic medications were asked open ended questions to determine the reasons for non-adherence to diabetic medications. Quality of life was assessed using WHOQOL-BREF questionnaire.

Data Analysis: The collected data was entered MS Excel Office-16 and data was analyzed using IBM -SPSS 20 version (Trial). The adherence was expressed in percentage and relationship with various factors were explored using Chi Square (χ^2) statistical tests of significance, P value <0.05 at two sided is considered as statistical significance.

Observations and Results

The findings of this study are based upon 303 participants. Majority of participants were in aged above 50 years, accounting for 41.59%. Participants aged between 31–40 years and 41–50 years each represented 23.76%, while the 20–30 age groups comprised only 10.89%. The highest proportion had illiterate (31.03%), followed by those who had completed high school 23.10% and graduation 20.79%. Only 2.64% had attained postgraduate education. A smaller number had completed higher secondary/ intermediate education 10.89%, middle school 5.94%, and primary school 5.61%. A vast majority of the participants were Hindu, comprising 88.45% of the sample. The remaining 11.55% were Muslim. No other religions were reported among the participants. Majority belonged to the other Backward Classes (OBC), comprising 57.76%. Participants from the General category accounted for 35.97%, while those from the Scheduled Castes (SC) made up 6.27%. The maximum participants 96.70% lived in Pucca houses and small proportion resided in Kutchha 2.63% and mixed-type houses 0.67%, indicating a high percent of stable housing among the participants. The majority were unmarried 80.86%, smaller proportions were widowed 12.87%, while 4.95% were married, only 1.32% were divorced. More than half (53.46%) belonged to the upper socioeconomic class, while 43.56% were categorized under the middle socioeconomic class. A small proportion, only 2.98%, fell into the lower socioeconomic category (**Table-1**).

Table- 1: Frequency distribution of study subjects as per their Socio-demographic characteristics (N=303).

Socio-demographic characteristics		No.	%
Age groups (in years)	20-30	33	10.89
	31-40	72	23.76
	41-50	72	23.76
	>50	126	41.59
Religion	Hindu	268	88.45
	Muslim	35	11.55
Caste	General	109	35.97
	OBC	175	57.76
	SC	19	6.27
House Type	Pucca	293	96.70
	Kutchra	8	2.63
	Mixed	2	0.67
Level of Education	Illiterate	94	31.03
	Primary school	17	5.61
	Middle school	18	5.94
	High school	70	23.10
	Higher Secondary/ Intermediate	33	10.89
	Graduation	63	20.79
	Post-graduation	8	2.64
Marital status	Married	15	4.95
	Unmarried	245	80.86
	Divorced	4	1.32
	Widowed	39	12.87
Socio-economic status	Lower	9	2.98
	Middle	132	43.56
	Upper	162	53.46

Distribution of respondents as per occupation of their head of the household is presented in table 2 which shows that three out of ten were unemployed and approximately same were engaged in skill works.

Table-2: Distribution of the participants according to occupation of the head of family (N=303).

Occupation of the Head of Family	No.	%
Professionals	16	5.28
Technicians and associate professionals	17	5.61
Clerks	20	6.60
Skilled workers and shop and market sales workers	46	15.18
Skilled agricultural and fishery workers	47	15.51
Craft and related trade workers	11	3.63
Plant and machine operators and assemblers	17	5.61
Elementary occupation	38	12.54
Unemployed	91	30.04

Distribution of respondents as per their education level and medical adherence is illustrated in table 3. Among illiterate respondents medication adherence was present in only 11.7% which was lowest and it was highest 87.50% in post graduation. This shows that medication adherence increases as education level increases and the statistically positive association between education level and medical adherence $p < 0.001$.

Table-3: Association of Medication Adherence with Education Level (N=303)

Education Level	Medication Adherence				Total (N=303)	
	Present (N=107)		Absent (N=196)		No.	%
	No.	%	No.	%		
Illiterate	11	11.70	83	88.30	94	31.03
Primary School	3	17.65	14	82.35	17	5.94
Middle School	5	27.78	13	72.22	18	5.94
High School	25	35.71	45	64.29	70	23.10
Intermediate	18	54.55	15	45.45	33	10.89
Graduation	38	60.32	25	39.68	63	20.79
Post graduation	7	87.50	1	12.50	8	2.64

$\chi^2 = 101.39$; $p < 0.001$

As per **Table- 4**, it shows that medical adherence was absent in mostly lower socio-economic status (66.67%) and present in upper socio-economic status (40.74%) $\chi^2 = 2.15$; $p = 0.34$ (NS). This shows that there is no statistically significant association between socio economic status and medical adherence. Maximum (40.38%) medical adherence was present in joint/ extended family while it was lowest (21.43%) in three generation family. There was no significant association was observed ($\chi^2 = 5.68$; $p = 0.06$).

Table- 4: Association between Socioeconomic Status and Medication Adherence (N=303)

Socio- economic characteristics		Medication Adherence				Total (N=303)		χ^2 & P value
		Present (N=107)		Absent (N=196)		No.	%	
		No.	%	No.	%			
Socio-economic status	Lower	3	33.33	6	66.67	9	2.98	$\chi^2 = 2.15$; $p = 0.34$ (NS)
	Middle	40	30.30	92	69.70	132	43.56	
	Upper	46	40.74	106	59.26	162	53.46	
Type of Family	Nuclear	36	34.29	69	65.71	105	34.65	$\chi^2 = 5.68$; $p = 0.06$
	Joint/Extended	63	40.38	93	59.62	156	51.49	
	Three-generation	9	21.43	34	78.57	42	13.86	

Table-5: Distribution of respondents as per their age- groups and medication adherence

Age Group (in years)	Medication Adherence			
	Present (N=107)		Absent (N=196)	
	No.	%	No.	%
20-30	14	42.42	19	57.58
31-40	28	38.89	44	61.11
41-50	29	40.28	43	59.72
>50	36	28.57	90	71.43
$\chi^2 = 4.42$; $p = 0.22$ (Not Significant)				

The distribution of medication adherence across different age groups is shown in **Table-5**. Among the total participants, in the age- group 20–30 years medication adherence was present in 42.42%, in the age group 31–40 years 38.89%, in the age

group 41–50 years 40.28% and aged >50 years and above 28.57%. This indicates that the highest number of participants with absent medication adherence was in the oldest age group 50 years and above. There is no statistically significant associations was found between age group and medication adherence $\chi^2= 4.42$; $p=0.22$

Figure-1: Age Group wise Medication Adherence

Table-6: Association of quality of life status with medication adherence

Study variables		Medication Adherence				χ^2 & P value
		Present (N=107)		Absent (N=196)		
		No.	%	No.	%	
Quality of life scores	Low	6	9.37	58	90.63	$\chi^2= 55.66$; $p<0.001$ (Significant)
	Medium	49	30.25	113	69.75	
	High	52	67.53	25	32.47	
Occupation of Head of Family	Professionals	10	62.50	6	37.50	$\chi^2= 32.20$; $p<0.001$ (Significant)
	Technicians & associate professionals	6	35.29	11	64.71	
	Clerks	6	30.00	14	70.00	
	Skilled workers and shop and market sales workers	22	47.83	24	52.17	
	Skilled agricultural and fishery workers	16	34.04	31	65.96	
	Craft and related trade workers	6	54.55	5	45.45	
	Plant and machine operators and assemblers	12	70.59	5	29.41	
	Elementary occupation	13	34.21	25	65.79	
	Unemployed	16	17.58	75	82.42	

Among respondents having low quality of life score medical adherence was present in 9.38%, in medium quality of life 30.25% and in high quality of life 67.53%. This shows that as quality of life score increases present of medication adherence also increases and the association between them was found statistically significant ($\chi^2= 55.66$; $p<0.001$) (Table-6). The respondents whose head of family occupation having plant and machine operators and assemblers had maximum (70.59%) present of medication adherence while it was lowest (17.58%) in unemployed respondents. There is significant association between Occupation of Head of Family and medication adherence ($\chi^2= 32.20$; $p<0.001$).

Total Quality Score=4; Physical Percentage + Psychological Percentage+ Social Percentage + Environmental Percentage.

Number of Samples per Group: Since we have 303 T2 DM patients and these were divided into 4 groups:

- **Group 1: 0-25%** : Lower adherence quality (roughly 75 samples).
- **Group 2: 26-50%** : Moderate adherence quality (roughly 75 samples).
- **Group 3: 51-75%** : Good adherence quality (roughly 75 samples).
- **Group 4: 76-100%** : Excellent adherence quality (roughly 75 samples).

Table-7: Relationship between Medical Adherence and Total Quality Score

Percentile Range		Total Score Range	Medical Adherence			
			Present		Absent	
			No.	%	No.	%
Group 1	0 - 25.0	56	32	57.14	24	42.86
Group 2	25.01 - 50.0	117	46	39.32	71	60.68
Group 3	50.01 - 75.0	98	21	21.43	77	78.57
Group 4	75.1 - 100.0	32	8	25.0	24	75.0
Total			107	35.31	196	64.69
$\chi^2 = 22.26; p < 0.001$						

Discussion

The discussion is based on 303 diabetic type 2 patients residing in urban area of Prayagraj District, Uttar Pradesh, India. More two fifth respondents were in the age group more than 50 years. The maximum percentages of respondents were in education level of high school followed by graduation. The lowest percentages of respondents were in the postgraduate qualification. Similar results were also supported by different authors^{8,9,10,11,12,13}, respectively.

The caste category wise distribution of the respondents focused that more half respondents were in other backward class. More than 80% respondents were married and only 5% were unmarried and rest were divorced / widow or widowers. Approximately similar findings were also reported by the authors.^{14,15} The distribution of respondents as per their living in the type of house showed that more 95%, respondents were in pucca houses and remaining were living in either Kucha house or mixed house and some studies also reported the distribution as per their living in the type of houses^{8, 9, 10, 11,15, 13}. Approximately more than 50% respondents were in upper socio-economic status group and very few respondents (3%) were in lower socio-economic group. The studies reported by several authors such as^{8, 9,10,11, 15, 13}.

The study highlights positive association of educational level with high medical adherence. This study focused that more 60% respondents having qualifications graduate or more had medical adherence. Respondents having no formal education only 12% had no formal education only 12% had medical adherence. The other studies found the similar pattern of medical adherence.^{8, 9} The occupation of the head of the household showed that maximum respondents had occupation of head of the household as skilled workers, shop, market sales, agriculture and fisheries workers. Approximately 7% respondents had their head of the household as plant and machine operators, assemblers and elementary occupation. The findings of the studies conducted by different authors^{8,9,10,13,14} had also described the distribution of the respondents as per occupation of the head of the household and similarly findings were reported.

The findings suggest that the medical adherence is not significantly associated with the socio-economic status of the respondents. Maximum adherence was found in upper socio-economic status. Not many studies were reported the distribution as per the occupation of the head of the household^{15, 14}. The medication adherence was observed in the generation type of family whereas about 40% were in joint/ extended family. The findings related to medical adherence as per their type of family reported by few authors^{9, 10, 15, 16, 17, 14}.

. The maximum adherence was found in the age group 20-30 years followed by the age groups 41-50 years. These findings suggest that the adherence was observed in the younger age group. These findings also suggested by the several authors^{19, 8, 9, 10, 16, 13, 17, 14}.

The distribution of respondents as per medical adherence and quality of life. The respondents having better quality of life had high adherence. About two- third respondents having high quality of life had higher better high adherence. Very few adherence c was observed among low quality of life patients. Several authors had also reported similar findings^{10, 11, 12, 16, 17, 18}.

The adherence is also associated with the occupation of the head of the household. Maximum adherence was found in about 70% respondents having head of the household as plant and machine operators and assemblers followed in the respondents whose head of the house hold occupation is unemployed^{8, 9, 10, 13, 17}. The motivation level of the respondents highlights that approximately two – fifth responds had low motivation. The distribution of respondents as per their motivation level are also concluded by the different authors.^{9, 10, 12, 16, 14}

Conclusion

The summary and conclusion are based 303 Type II DM patients residing in Prayagraj Urban area. About two- fifth participants were in the age group 50 years and above while only 10.89% were in the group of 20-30 years. No formal education had 31.03% participants, approximately one fourth participants had their education level graduation and above. One third respondents were in the education level of High School and Intermediate. 88.45 participants were belonging to Hindu religion and remaining were in Muslims. More than fifty percents were in other backward classes and more than one third were in general caste category.

As per marital status, approximately four fifth participants were married and one eight were divorced / widows etc. Almost all study subjects were living in Pucca house and only 3.3 percent were residing in Kutcha and mixed type of house. More than fifty participants were in upper socio-economic status, only 3% were in lower socio-economic status. The medical adherence was found in approximately more one third participants (35.31%) as compared to 64.67% were in less medical adherence. These results conclude that as education level increases the positivity of medical adherence is also increasingly. This shows that association of education is positively associated with high medical adherences.

The socio-economic status is also affecting the positively of medical adherences. In upper socio-economic class approximately two fifth were in high medical adherence. Type of family is also associated with medical adherence. In the joint / extended family, approximately two- fifth respondents were in high medical adherence but it was conclude the statistical significant association.

The expenditures were made on drugs/ medicines, transport to health facility and consultation fee. All study subjects expend on consultation fee under Rs.500/- per month. About four-fifth responds expend on transport to health facility, under Rs.500/- per month whereas more than 80% respondents expend on drugs/ medicine under Rs.500-1000 per month. About two-fifth respondents in the age group 20-50 years were in high medical adherence. In the age group more than 50 years, the low medical adherence was very high. More than half respondent were in medicine partly life. Approximately two third respondents had high adherence in high quality of life. The positivity of medical adherence is also increasing as the quality of life increasing.

High adherence was found about three fourth participants in plumbing. In professional participants more three-fifth were in high adherence. The participants who are not working at present had high adherence is very low (18.0%). It concludes that adherence is statically significantly association with occupation and the respondents. Morethan one third (35%) participants had high knowledge. In the younger group 10-30 years two- third had high knowledge. It also concludes that as ages increase the proportion of high knowledge respondents were decreasing. Approximately two-third participants had their glycemic control level and other had poorly control of glycemic level. About one-third respondents had high knowledge in both well and controlled glycemic level.

As per motivations, levels, about two-third participants had low motivation and other had high motivation level. Only 35% participants had high medicine adherence and other were in low medicine adherence. The quality of life score is categorized in quartiles. About two –fifth participants were in second quartile of quality of life score and very few 10% participants were in fourth quartile of quality of life score.

Reference

1. World Health Organization. Diabetes [Internet]. World Health Organisation. WHO; 2023. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/diabetes>.
2. Kasper DL, Fauci AS, Hauser SL, Longo DL, Jameson JL, Loscalzo J. Diabetes Mellitus [Internet]. 19th ed. Access Medicine. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Education; 2016. Available from: <https://accessmedicine.mhmedical.com/content.aspx?bookid=1820§ionid=127559730>.
3. Aravindakshan R, Abraham SB, Aiyappan R. Medication Adherence to Oral Hypoglycemic Drugs among Individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus - A Community Study. *Indian J Community Med*. 2021 Jul-Sep; 46 (3):503-507.
4. Nandini HC, Gali A, Muraraiah S. Assessment of factors influencing adherence to antidiabetic drugs among patients with Type 2 diabetes mellitus at a tertiary care hospital in India. *Pharmacology and Clinical Pharmacy Research*. 2020 Apr 1; 5 (1): 7-13.
5. Mishra R, Sharma SK, Verma R, Kangra P, Dahiya P, Kumari P, Sahu P, Bhakar P, Kumawat R, Kaur R, Kaur R, Kant R. Medication adherence and quality of life among type-2 diabetes mellitus patients in India. *World J Diabetes*. 2021 Oct 15; 12 (10):1740-1749.
6. Sahoo J, Mohanty S, Kundu A, Epari V. Medication Adherence Among Patients of Type II Diabetes Mellitus and Its Associated Risk Factors: A Cross-Sectional Study in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Eastern India. *Cureus*. 2022 Dec 29;14 (12).
7. Kavitha S, Nalini GK, Suresh RM, Sahana GN, Deepak P, Nagaral JV. Treatment adherence and factors contributing to non adherence among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients in a tertiary care hospital: a cross sectional study. *Int J Basic Clin Pharmacol*. 2017 Feb 24; 6 (3): 689-94.
8. Polonsky WH, Henry RR. Poor medication adherence in type 2 diabetes: recognizing the scope of the problem and its key contributors. *Patient preference and adherence*. 2016 Jul 22:1299-307.
9. Awodele O, Osuolale J. Medication adherence in type 2 diabetes patients: study of patients in Alimosho General Hospital, Igando, Lagos, Nigeria. *African Health Sciences*. 2015 May 28;15(2):513.
10. Kirkman MS, Rowan-Martin MT, Levin R, Fonseca VA, Schmittiel JA, Herman WH, Aubert RE. Determinants of adherence to diabetes medications: findings from a large pharmacy claims database. *Diabetes care*. 2015 Apr 1; 38 (4): 604-9.
11. Sahoo J, Mohanty S, Kundu A, Epari V. Medication Adherence Among Patients of Type II Diabetes Mellitus and Its Associated Risk Factors: A Cross-Sectional Study in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Eastern India. *Cureus*. 2022 Dec 29; 14 (12).
12. Mishra R, Sharma SK, Verma R, Kangra P, Dahiya P, Kumari P, Sahu P, Bhakar P, Kumawat R, Kaur R, Kaur R, Kant R. Medication adherence and quality of life among type-2 diabetes mellitus patients in India. *World J Diabetes*. 2021 Oct 15; 12 (10):1740-1749.
13. Nandini HC, Gali A, Muraraiah S. Assessment of factors influencing adherence to antidiabetic drugs among patients with Type 2 diabetes mellitus at a tertiary care hospital in India. *Pharmacology and Clinical Pharmacy Research*. 2020 Apr 1;5(1):7 13.
14. Vallepalli C, Sekhar KC, Kumar UV, Gogineni SS, Popuri V, Deotale PG. A Study on Adherence of Medication among Diabetic Individuals of Ashoknagar of Eluru, Andhra Pradesh.
15. Olickal JJ, Chinnakali P, Suryanarayana BS, Saya GK, Ganapathy K, Subrahmanyam DKS. Medication adherence and glycemic control status among people with diabetes seeking care from a tertiary care teaching hospital, south India. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*. 2021 Jul; 11:100742.
16. Maheshwari U, Sowmiya KR, Kavin S. Self care practices among type II diabetics attending primary health centre, Thiruvallur district, Tamil Nadu. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2017 Aug; 4: 2745-9.
17. Sekhar CC, Babu DS, Krishna GA, Deepthi CS, Kalluri JB. A Study on Assessment of Level of Self-Care Practices among Known Type 2 Diabetes Patients in Rural Field Practice Area of South India. *International Journal of Medicine and Public Health*. 2020; 10 (1).
18. Waari G, Mutai J, Gikunju J. Medication adherence and factors associated with poor adherence among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients on follow-up at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2018; 29.